

CGG crystals for control of electromagnetic radiation

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Abstract – Based on polarization-optical measurements and the values of the two main absolute piezo-optical coefficients, the main components of the matrix of the piezo-optical effect of calcium gallogermanate CGG crystals are determined. Based on them, the optimal conditions of photoelastic interaction are determined and the geometries of sensitive elements for electromagnetic radiation modulators are proposed.

Keywords – photoelastic modulator, piezo-optical effect, langasite crystals, calcium gallogermanate.

I. INTRODUCTION

To control optical radiation in the ultraviolet (UV) region of the spectrum, modulators are used, the sensitive element of which is quartz [1]. This material is still out of competition, as it is characterized by a set of physical properties necessary for acousto-optics: wide transmission range, resistance to powerful electromagnetic radiation, large piezoelectric coefficients [2]. However, the disadvantages of quartz are low acousto-optical efficiency and relatively high attenuation of acoustic waves [3]. Therefore, the task of finding effective acousto-optical (AO) materials for controlling high-power radiation in the UV region of the spectrum is relevant.

Crystals of the lanthanum-gallium silicate group $\text{La}_3\text{Ga}_5\text{SiO}_{14}$ (LGS) reveal a unique combination of different physical properties that make these crystals promising for application. For example, they are characterized by the stability of physical characteristics, in particular elastic [4], as well as large piezoelectric effect and coefficients of electromechanical coupling [5]. These characteristics have made LGS crystals popular for the development of acoustoelectronic devices [6,7]. Since these crystals reveal a high threshold of optical damage of ~ 1 Gw [7], low attenuation of acoustic waves (several times lower than in quartz [3]), there is a possibility and feasibility to use these crystals as sensitive elements in acousto-optical devices for telecommunication systems.

II. RELATIONS FOR THE CALCULATION OF POCs

To evaluate the photoelastic efficiency of the calcium gallogermanate crystal $\text{Ca}_3\text{Ga}_2\text{Ge}_4\text{O}_{14}$ (CGG), it is necessary to determine all components of the π_{im} matrix of elasto-optical

coefficients (EOCs).

Elasto-optic coefficients p_{ik} (EOCs) are calculated on the basis of the known tensor relation $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{C}\boldsymbol{\pi}$, where $\mathbf{C}$ is a matrix of elastic stiffness coefficients, $\boldsymbol{\pi}$ is a matrix of piezo-optic coefficients (POCs). The piezo-optical effect (POE) in crystals are studied by interferometric technique [8–10]. These technique are too time consuming, so an attempt to obtain absolute piezo-optical coefficients π_{im} based on polarization-optical measurements is justified. There are few successful examples of this method before. As a rule, such works were limited to the determination of diagonal turning-shear POCs in tetragonal and cubic crystals [11,12]. An effective example is the study of POE in crystals of Rochelle salt [13], which belong to the orthorhombic class of symmetry 222 and have 12 independent POC. However, the author of [13] does not claim that the absolute POC π_{im} is determined only by the polarization-optical method. To fill the POC matrix, six main POCs were also determined by the interferometric method and, in addition, the ratio of some elasto-optical coefficients p_{ik} was found by the acousto-diffraction method. In paper [14], it is claimed that for crystals of $3m$ point group the matrix of absolute POCs can be completed only on the basis of polarization-optical studies. However, it is not true. Based on the known system of equations [15]

$$\pi_{31}^* = \pi_{11}n_1^3 - \pi_{12}n_1^3, \quad (1)$$

$$\pi_{21}^* = \pi_{31}n_3^3 - \pi_{11}n_1^3, \quad (2)$$

$$\pi_{41}^* = 0.5(\pi_{12} + \pi_{31} - 2\pi_{41})n_4^3 - \pi_{11}n_1^3 \quad (3)$$

(where π_{41}^* , π_{21}^* , π_{31}^* is POCs of birefringence, n_i is refraction index, $i = 1, 2, 3, 4$) it is impossible to find absolute POCs π_{11} , π_{12} i π_{31} . For example, writing on the basis of equations (1), (2) the relations for π_{12} , π_{31} and substituting them in (3), we obtain the equation for the determination of POC π_{11} on the basis of POCs of birefringence π_{41}^* , π_{21}^* , π_{31}^* :

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$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{41}^* &= 0.5(\pi_{21}^* - \pi_{31}^*) \frac{n_4^3}{n_3^3} - \pi_{41} \cdot n_4^3 + \\ &+ 0.5\pi_{11}(n_4^3 + \frac{n_1^3 n_4^3}{n_3^3} - 2n_1^3), \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where the combination of refractive indices n_i near the coefficient π_{11} and the corresponding term tend to zero. The latter statement is all the more true for crystals of the langasite group, since the difference between the refractive indices n_1, n_3, n_4 in these crystals is very small [3]. Therefore, in order to find all eight absolute POCs π_{im} of the CGG crystals by the polarization-optical method, it is also necessary to perform at least two interferometric measurements.

Let write the relations for establishing the POC matrix on the basis of the POC of the path difference of the course π_{km}^o taking into account the signs of these POCs. To do this, we use the rule of determining the signs of the mechanical stress-induced path difference for cases of beam propagation both along the optical axis and perpendicular to it.

We use the known expression for interconnection between the POC of path difference π_{km}^o and POC of birefringence π_{km}^* [10, 16]:

$$\pi_{km}^o = -2 \frac{\delta \Delta n_k}{\sigma_m} + 2\Delta n_k S_{km} = \pi_{km}^* - 2\Delta n_k S_{km}, \quad (5)$$

where $\pi_{km}^o = -2\delta \Delta n_k / (d_k \sigma_m)$, $\delta \Delta n_k$ is a path difference induced by the uniaxial pressure, d_k is a thickness of a sample, σ_m is a mechanical stress, Δn_k is birefringence, $\delta \Delta n_k$ is a change of birefringence induced by uniaxial pressure, S_{km} is elastic compliance coefficients.

In the half-wave stress method we have: $\delta \Delta n_k = \lambda/2$ (λ is light wavelength). Thus $\pi_{km}^o = -\lambda / (d_k \sigma_{km}) = -\lambda / \sigma_{km}^o$, (σ_{km}^o is a half-wave stress, $\sigma_{km}^o = d_k \sigma_{km}$ is a control stress).

If we write $\delta \Delta n_k$ in (5) as $\delta \Delta n_k = \delta n_i - \delta n_j$ and use the main equation of static photo-elasticity (piezo-optics) $\delta n_i = -\pi_{im} \cdot \sigma_m \cdot n_i^3 / 2$ (δn_i is a change of refractive index caused by mechanical stress σ_m), the following expression is obtained: $\pi_{km}^* = \pi_{im} n_i^3 - \pi_{jm} n_j^3$ [15], where n_i, n_j is refraction indices for two mutually perpendicular light waves propagating in the crystal in the k direction. Substituting this expression in (5), we obtain:

$$\pi_{km}^o = \pi_{im} n_i^3 - \pi_{jm} n_j^3 - 2\Delta n_k S_{km}. \quad (6)$$

Base on this equation, the expression for determination of main POCs $\pi_{11}, \pi_{12}, \pi_{13}, \pi_{31}$ and π_{33} for crystals of 32, 3m and $\bar{3}m$ symmetry are obtained for direct cut samples (the edges are perpendicular to crystal-optics axes X_1, X_2, X_3) taking into account the elasticity [16]:

$$\pi_{23}^o \equiv \pi_{13}^o = \pi_{33} n_3^3 - \pi_{13} n_1^3 - 2\Delta n_2 S_{23}, \quad (7)$$

$$\pi_{21}^o \equiv \pi_{12}^o = \pi_{31} n_3^3 - \pi_{11} n_1^3 - 2\Delta n_2 S_{21}, \quad (8)$$

$$\pi_{31}^o \equiv \pi_{32}^o = (\pi_{21} - \pi_{11}) n_1^3 \equiv (\pi_{11} - \pi_{12}) n_1^3. \quad (9)$$

The last equation does not contain an elastic term, because in the corresponding expression $2\Delta n_3 S_{km}$ the value of birefringence $\Delta n_3 = 0$. From this equation the value of coefficient π_{66} : $\pi_{66} = \pi_{11} - \pi_{12} = \pi_{31}^o / n_1^3$ can also be determined.

Three equations (7) – (9) are not enough to determine the five independent POCs included in this system of equations. The description of the geometries of the piezo-optical interaction experiment on 45°-cut samples is reduced to systems of equations of type (1) – (3), which are dependent, as proved above, and therefore it is impossible to determine the main π_{im} . Therefore, two main POCs need to be found by the interferometric technique.

Non-principal POCs π_{14}, π_{41} and π_{44} are calculated from POCs π_{km}^o determined on $X_1/45^\circ$ -cut sample (see fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The scheme of $X/45^\circ$ -cut sample for investigation of piezo-optic effect in crystals of 32, 3m, $\bar{3}m$ point groups.

The corresponding expressions are:

$$\pi_{14}^o - \pi_{14}^o = n_1^3 \pi_{14} - 2\Delta n_1 S_{14}, \quad (10)$$

$$\pi_{41}^o - \pi_{41}^o = 2n_4^3 \pi_{41} + 2\Delta n_4 S_{14}, \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \pi_{44}^o + \pi_{44}^o &= 0.5n_4^3(\pi_{11} + \pi_{13} + \pi_{31} + \pi_{33} + 2\pi_{44}) - n_1^3(\pi_{12} + \pi_{13}) - \\ &- \Delta n_4(S_{11} + 2S_{13} + S_{33} - S_{44}). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The experimental conditions for each of these equations and the essence of directions 4 and $\bar{4}$ are clear from fig. 1; $n_4 = n_{\bar{4}}$ are refractive indices along directions $i = 4$ and $i = \bar{4}$ described by known expression $n_4 = n_{\bar{4}} = \sqrt{2}n_1 n_3 / (n_1^2 + n_3^2)^{1/2}$.

Therefore, using equations (7) – (12), as well as the values obtained experimentally by polarization-optical method of the corresponding POCs of the path difference π_{km}^o and at least two values of absolute POCs π_{im} , we can calculate the remaining 6 independent POCs for crystals of 32, 3m and $\bar{3}m$ symmetry. Two values of absolute POCs (π_{11} and π_{33}) for the calculation of the full POC matrix for CGG crystals in this work were obtained experimentally by interferometric technique.

III. METHOD OF EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

POCs of path differences π_{km}^o necessary for the calculation of the absolute POCs of the calcium gallogermanate crystals were obtained by the polarization-optical method in reflected light. The scheme of set-up is given in fig. 2.

The polarized beam is reflected from the back side of the sample 3 and after reflection from the translucent mirror 2 passes through the analyzer and enters the photodetector.

Fig. 2. Scheme of polarization-optical set-up for determination of POC π°_{km} in reflected light: 1 - laser, 2 - translucent mirror, 3 - sample, 4 - analyzer, 5 - photodetector, 6 - measuring device, 7 - mirror.

Since the beam passes through the sample 2 times, the half-wave stress σ_{km} is 2 times smaller than in the case of the known polarization-optical method of half-wave stresses. The method is especially relevant in the case when the half-wave stresses are commensurate with the mechanical strength of the crystal.

Since the refractive indices of the crystals are relatively small, the reflection coefficient $r_o = (n_m - 1)/(n_m + 1)$ [17] and the intensity of the reflected beam (it is proportional to r_o^2) relative to the incident beam for CGG are also small:

$$r_o^2 = \frac{(n_m - 1)^2}{(n_m + 1)^2} = \frac{(0,816)^2}{(2,816)^2} \approx 0,08 \text{ або } 8\%; \quad (13)$$

where n_m is an average value between the refractive indices n_o and n_e . However, the specified light intensity is quite sufficient for its objective analysis by photodetectors. Note that in the case of the investigation of CGG crystals, a reflective mirror was placed after the studied sample 3 (fig. 2).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of polarization-optical investigations are indicated in Table 1.

TABLE I. CONTROL MECHANICAL STRESSES σ°_{km} (kgf/cm) AND POCs OF PATH DIFFERENCE π°_{km} (Br = 10^{-12} m²/N) FOR CGG CRYSTALS AT $\lambda = 633$ nm AND $T = 20$ °C

σ°_{21}	98	π°_{21}	6.59 ± 0.46
σ°_{23}	101	π°_{23}	-6.39 ± 0.45
σ°_{31}	520	π°_{31}	-1.24 ± 0.09

The signs of the control stresses σ°_{km} and, accordingly, of the POCs of path difference π°_{km} are determined on the basis of a known rule: if the mechanical stress σ_m increases the natural path difference Δ_k , the sign of the path difference $\delta\Delta_k$ is positive (and vice versa). The increase or decrease of Δ_k under the stress of σ_m was determined using the compensator of the path difference (quartz wedge).

Note that the elastic contribution $2\Delta n_k S_{km}$ to the value of π°_{km} (see equation (6) – (9)) in the polarization-optical experiment is small and does not exceed 3% of the value of π°_{km} , which is due

to small values birefringence Δn_k of these crystals. That is, within the error of the polarization-optical experiment ($\sim 7\%$) for crystals of the langasite group, the following equality is valid: $\pi^{\circ}_{km} = \pi^*_{km}$. However, in order to obtain exact values of absolute POCs π_{im} , elastic contributions are taken into account.

The values of POCs π_{11} and π_{33} obtained by the interferometric technique (based on the Mach–Zehnder interferometer) [8–10,17,18] and independent main POCs π_{12} , π_{13} та π_{31} calculated on the basis of POC of path difference are given in Table 2. Absolute POCs π_{11} and π_{33} are selected for the calculations as the ones with the smallest error.

TABLE II. ABSOLUTE POCs π_{im} AND ELOCs p_{ik} OF CGG CRYSTALS AT $\lambda = 633$ nm AND $T = 20$ °C

π_{im} , Br	π_{11}	π_{12}	π_{13}	π_{31}	π_{33}
Polarization-optical meas.	-0.30 ±0.07	-0.09 ±0.07	0.27 ±0.09	0.77 ±0.10	-0.80 ±0.04
p_{ik}	p_{11}	p_{12}	p_{13}	p_{31}	p_{33}
Calculated	-0.032 ±0.015	-0.024 ±0.014	0.036 ±0.023	0.126 ±0.020	-0.081 ±0.017

Note: highlighted values of POCs were determined by interferometric technique.

The absolute POCs π_{im} of calcium gallogermanate were calculated in accordance with equations (7)–(9) on the basis of the values of the elastic compliance coefficients S_{km} and the refractive indices n_i taken from [3]: $S_{23} = S_{13} = -1.54$, $S_{21} = S_{12} = -5.19 \cdot 10^{-12}$ m²/N; $n_1 = n_o = 1.808$. The calculation of non-principal POCs π_{im} (π_{14} , π_{41} and π_{44}) on the basis of complex expressions (10) – (12) did not give a positive result: errors in determining these coefficients exceed their values. Therefore, in the future it is planned to realize thorough interferometric studies of these POCs on the basis of the maximum possible number of experimental conditions with proving the reliability of the research results, as done, for example, in [8,9].

Elasto-optic coefficients (ELOCs) p_{ik} were calculated in accordance with the known tensor expression $p_{ik} = \pi_{im} C_{mk}$, e.g. $p_{13} = (\pi_{11} + \pi_{12})C_{13} + \pi_{13}C_{33}$, etc. The values of the elastic stiffness coefficients C_{mk} of CGG crystals were taken from paper [3]: $C_{13} = 7.29$, $C_{33} = 23.96 \cdot 10^{10}$ N/m², etc. The error of specified value of p_{ik} was calculated as the mean square value of the product of π_{im} and C_{mk} in accordance with the known expression $\delta(\pi_{im} \cdot C_{mk}) = [(\delta\pi_{im} \cdot C_{mk})^2 + (\pi_{im} \cdot \delta C_{mk})^2]^{1/2}$ applied to each of the terms included in the expression for p_{ik} .

As it is seen from Table 2, the largest elasto-optical effect corresponds to the coefficient $p_{31} = 0.126$. Let us calculate the acousto-optical (AO) efficiency of the CGG crystal, based on this value of ELOC and the expression for the AO figure-of-merit:

$$M_2 = n_i^6 p_{ik}^2 / (\rho V_k^3). \quad (14)$$

Substituting in (14) the mentioned value of p_{31} , refractive index $n_3 = 1.824$, crystal density $\rho = 4589$ kg/m³ [3] and the velocity of the longitudinal acoustic wave $V_3 = 5857$ m/s, we obtain the value of $M_2 = 0.63 \cdot 10^{-15}$ s³/kg. This is a relatively

small value of M_2 . Higher AO efficiency is typical for the transverse acoustic wave, which propagates in the main plane X_2, X_3 due to the significantly lower value of the acoustic wave velocity ($V = 3328$ m/s). The corresponding value of $M_2 = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-15}$ s³/kg (according to our data) is commensurate with the M_2 of quartz crystals [19] used in AO devices in the ultraviolet range of the spectrum. However, the CGG crystal due to such characteristics as excellent optical quality, high mechanical strength (~ 2000 kg/cm², according to our data), high resistance to environmental aggression, and, most importantly, low attenuation of acoustic waves [3] (much lower than in quartz) can successfully compete with quartz as a promising AO material for the UV region of the spectrum.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The POCs of the path difference π_{km}^o is determined and on their basis the main components of the matrix of absolute POCs π_{im} . On the basis of these POCs and elastic stiffness coefficients C_{km} , the main components of the matrix of elasto-optical coefficients p_{ik} are calculated.

The largest value of the elasto-optical effect in CGG crystals is determined by the coefficient $p_{31} = 0.12$. The highest AO efficiency of this crystal ($M_2 = 2.2 \cdot 10^{-15}$ s³/kg) corresponds to the shear acoustic wave propagating in the main plane X_2, X_3 . This value of M_2 is commensurate with M_2 of quartz crystals [19], which are used in AO devices for modulating light of the UV spectral range. But the CGG crystal, due to its excellent optical quality, ultra-high mechanical strength, resistance to environmental aggression, and, most importantly, low attenuation of acoustic waves, can successfully compete with quartz as a promising AO material for the UV spectrum.

Further study of the spatial anisotropy of the POE, ELOE and AO effects by the methods described in [20–25] will allow to determine the maximum possible values of these effects in CGG crystals and the corresponding geometries of their observation, as well as to obtain data on the maximum achievable AO efficiency of this material.

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